

What is hidden in e-waste: potential recycling opportunities

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The group of metals known as rare earth elements (REE) comprises the elements of the lanthanide series. The metals of the lanthanide series are: Lanthanum (La), cerium (Ce), praseodymium (Pr), neodymium (Nd), promethium (Pm), samarium (Sm), europium (Eu), gadolinium (Gd), terbium (Tb), dysprosium (Dy), holmium (Ho), erbium (Er), thulium (Tm), ytterbium (Yb) and lutetium (Lu). In addition, yttrium (Y) and scandium (Sc) are often grouped together with the lanthanides and referred to as REE (Australian Government, 2023).

REE resources are mainly associated with four geological environments: alkaline igneous rocks, carbonatites, placer deposits with monazite xenotime mineralization and clay deposits with ion adsorption (Australian Government, 2023). The rapid expansion of high-tech industries, such as those focused on new energy generation, storage, and electronic information, has driven global demand for rare earth elements (REEs), which are essential raw materials for these and other sectors. Data show that global production of rare earth minerals, including mining, smelting, and application, increased from 124,000 metric tonnes in 2015 to 390,000 metric tonnes in 2024, representing a 214% rise over the past decade. Moreover, large-scale mining, smelting, and industrial use of REEs have accelerated their biogeochemical cycling, resulting in significant accumulation in the atmosphere, water, soil, and living organisms. Given the continued growth of REE mining, processing, and use, the increasing concentration of these elements in urban environments and their potential health effects require urgent attention (Ma and Wu, 2025).

Table 1. An overview of the REE content in the selected e-waste models.

Source	REE concentration	Ecotoxicological information	Reference
Smartphone (Android/iOS)	Nd, Pr, Dy, Y, Eu, Tb (collectively): 0.02–0.08%	Informal recycling may release REEs and associated metals (Pb, Cu, Sb), contributing to soil and groundwater contamination. High turnover increases the global e-waste burden.	Balaram, 2019; Robinson, 2009; Forti et al., 2020
Feature phone	Nd, Pr, Y, Eu (collectively): 0.005–0.02%	Lower REE intensity; however, improper disposal may release hazardous metals that harm the environment and human health.	Robinson, 2009; Forti et al., 2020
E-scooter	Nd, Pr, Dy (collectively): 0.2–0.8%	Combined battery and magnet waste increases environmental risk and recycling complexity, but offers significant potential for urban mining.	Binnemans et al., 2013; Gaines, 2014; International energy agency, 2021

Drone	Nd, Pr, Dy (collectively): 0.3–1.2%	High REE intensity per unit mass; increasing demand puts pressure on supply chains and extraction impacts.	Binnemans et al, 2013; International energy agency, 2021
Microwave oven	Nd, Ce, La (collectively): 0.01–0.05%	Moderate contribution to bulk e-waste; environmental impact mainly arises from improper disposal and accumulation.	Balaram, 2019; Robinson, 2009
Hard disk drive (HDD)	2,500–15,000 ppm of Nd, Dy, and Pr collectively	Contains traces of lead, which can cause neurological damage, and cadmium, a carcinogen.	Liang et al., 2024; Chesapeake paper systems, n. d.; Lenntech, n. d.–a; Lenntech, n. d.–b
Fluorescent lamp	1,000–20,000 ppm of Y, Eu, Ce, Tb or La	Contains mercury in vapour form, which affects the nervous system and kidneys and is also teratogenic.	Liang et al., 2024; Viana et al., 2022; Lenntech, n. d.–c
Television	10–100 ppm of Y, Eu, and Tb collectively	Contains lead, which can cause neurological damage; cadmium, a carcinogen; and arsenic, which can cause changes in animal DNA.	Liang et al., 2024; Sunada recycling, 2025; Lenntech, n. d.–a; Lenntech, n. d.–b; Lenntech, n. d.–d

With the digitalisation of the developed world and the advancement of new medical technologies, REEs are now regarded as strategic metals in the global economy. Their use is therefore of increasing interest across various fields, from engineering to medicine. In medicine, they have become essential for a range of molecular imaging and radiotherapy procedures, while in interdisciplinary science, they are increasingly discussed in the context of recycling and reuse as part of the transition towards a circular economy.

For effective and responsible pre-recycling processes, it is crucial to have a detailed understanding of the chemical composition of materials containing REEs. Beyond the technical aspects, broader awareness of their environmental and societal impacts is also necessary. In this context, citizen science plays an important role by contributing to public engagement and awareness at multiple levels: from the safe use and composition of products, to recycling practices, and to systems for safe handling, disposal, and understanding impacts on living organisms. Science therefore has the responsibility to provide answers across the entire ecosystem and social spectrum, enabling the development of a safe and well-informed society grounded in responsible resource management.

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References

1. Australian Government, December 19, 2023. Rare earth elements. Available from: <https://www.ga.gov.au/scientific-topics/minerals/mineral-resources-and-advice/australian-resource-reviews/rare-earth-elements>
2. Balaram V. Rare earth elements: A review of applications, occurrence, exploration, analysis, recycling, and environmental impact. *Geosci Front.* 2019; 10(4), 1285–1303. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsf.2018.12.005>

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3. Binnemans K, Jones PT, Blanpain B, van Gerven T, et al. Recycling of rare earths: A critical review. *J Clean Prod.* 2013; 51: 1–22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.12.037> 52
53
 4. Chesapeake paper systems, n. d. The hidden dangers of DIY hard drive destruction. Available from: <https://chespaper.com/the-hidden-dangers-of-diy-hard-drive-destruction/> 54
55
 5. Forti V, Baldé CP, Kuehr R, Bel G, 2020. The Global E-waste Monitor 2020: Quantities, flows, and the circular economy potential. Available from: https://ewastemonitor.info/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/GEM_2020_def_july1_low.pdf 56
57
58
 6. Gaines L. The future of automotive lithium-ion battery recycling. *Sustain Mater Technol.* 2014; 1–2: 2–7. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susmat.2014.10.001> 59
60
 7. International energy agency, May 05, 2021. The role of critical minerals in clean energy transitions. Available from: <https://www.iea.org/reports/the-role-of-critical-minerals-in-clean-energy-transitions> 61
62
 8. Lenntech, n. d.–a. Lead – Pb, Chemical properties of lead – Health effects of lead – Environmental effects of lead. Available from: <https://www.lenntech.com/periodic/elements/pb.htm> 63
64
 9. Lenntech, n. d.–b. Lead – Pb, Cadmium – Cd, Chemical properties of cadmium – Health effects of cadmium – Environmental effects of cadmium. Available from: <https://www.lenntech.com/periodic/elements/cd.htm> 65
66
 10. Lenntech, n. d.–c. Mercury – Hg, Chemical properties of mercury – Health effects of mercury – Environmental effects of mercury. Available from: <https://www.lenntech.com/periodic/elements/hg.htm> 67
68
 11. Lenntech, n. d.–d. Arsenic – As, Chemical properties of arsenic – Health effects of arsenic – Environmental effects of arsenic. Available from: <https://www.lenntech.com/periodic/elements/as.htm> 69
70
 12. Liang B, Gu J, Zeng X, Yuan W, et al. A review of the occurrence and recovery of rare earth elements from electronic waste. *Molecules.* 2024; 29(19): 4624. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules29194624> 71
72
 13. Ma J, Wu F. Urban impact of rare earth elements. *Science.* 2025; 390: 684–684. DOI: 10.1126/science.aeb7692 73
 14. Robinson BH. E-waste: An assessment of global production and environmental impacts. *Sci Total Environ.* 2009; 408(2): 183–191. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.09.044> 74
75
 15. Sunada recycling, May 01, 2025. Is your TV hurting the environment? Here's what you need to know. Available from: <https://www.sunadarecycling.com/blog/old-tvs-and-environment-concerns> 76
77
 16. Viana LN, Senra Soares AP, Guimarães DL, Sandoval Rojano WJ, Dillenburg Saint'Pierre T. Fluorescent lamps: A review on environmental concerns and current recycling perspectives highlighting Hg and rare earth elements. 2022; 10(6): 108915. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2022.108915> 78
79
80
81